

**MEANS OF PHYSICAL CULTURE IN ENSURING THE WORKING CAPACITY
OF CADETS OF THE ACADEMY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract: Physical exercises contribute to the body's resistance to the effects of training loads, especially in conditions of emotionally stressful educational work. Physical exercises as a means of active recreation, "small forms" of physical culture, physical training are recommended to be used in order to increase the mental performance of students, to overcome and prevent psychoemotional and functional stress.

Keywords: physical culture, cadet, sport, professional training, training, micropause, energy consumption.

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The most important factor in ensuring the high quality of professional training of university graduates is the active educational and cognitive activity of cadets. This activity is a complex process in the conditions of objectively existing contradictions, which include:

- contradictions between a large amount of educational and scientific information and a lack of time to master it;
- between the objectively ongoing, gradual, long-term process of becoming a social maturity of a future specialist and the desire to assert themselves and prove themselves as quickly as possible;
- between the desire for independence in the selection of knowledge taking into account personal interests and the rigid framework of the curriculum and curricula.

These contradictions create high nervous and emotional tension, which negatively affects the health and, especially, the psychophysical state of the cadets.

The concept of "culture" can be defined as the degree of disclosure of a person's potential in various fields of activity. Culture is represented in the results of a person's material and spiritual activity; he learns the culture fixed in spiritual and material values, acts in the social environment as a carrier of cultural values, creates new values necessary for the development of culture of subsequent generations.

Objective and subjective factors also affect the psychophysical state of students. Objective factors include age, gender, state of health, the amount of

training load, the nature and duration of rest, etc. Subjective factors include the motivation of learning, the level of knowledge, the ability to adapt to new conditions of study at the university, psychophysical capabilities, neuropsychic stability, personal qualities (character, temperament, sociability, etc.), performance, fatigue, etc.

Physical culture is the basis of an individual's socio-cultural existence, a fundamental modification of his general and professional culture. As an integrated result of education and professional training, it manifests itself in a person's attitude to their health, physical abilities and abilities, in lifestyle and professional activity and appears in the unity of knowledge, beliefs, value orientations and in their practical implementation.

Physical culture is an organic part of universal culture, its special independent area. At the same time, it is "a mythical process and the result of human activity, a means and a way of physical improvement of the individual. Physical culture affects the vital aspects of the individual, obtained in the form of makings that are transmitted genetically and develop in the course of life under the influence of education, activities and the environment. Physical culture satisfies social needs in communication, play, entertainment, and in some forms of personal self-expression through socially active useful activity.

A serious test of the body is the information overload of cadets that occurs when studying numerous academic disciplines, the scientific level and information volume of which is constantly increasing.

Sport is a part of physical culture. In it, a person strives to expand the boundaries of his capabilities, this is a huge world of emotions generated by successes and failures, the most popular spectacle, an effective means of educating and self-education of a person, there is a complex process of interpersonal relations in it. Sport is actually a competitive activity and special preparation for it. He lives by certain rules and norms of behavior. It clearly shows the desire to win, to achieve high results, requiring the mobilization of physical, mental and moral qualities of a person. Therefore, they often talk about the athletic character of people who successfully manifest themselves in competitions. Satisfying a person's personal needs, sports become a physical and spiritual necessity.

Our research among first- and second-year cadets shows that 33% of cadets experience fatigue by the end of the week. It is expressed: eye fatigue - 22%, general nervous tension - 16%, headache - 13%, general passivity and depression - 16%. Of the causes of fatigue, 32% of respondents noted prolonged attention strain, 20% - great mental stress, 25% - the absence of short-term rest breaks during classes, 22% - work is done mainly sitting.

The mental and emotional (nervous) overstrain of an increasing number of people engaged in mental activity is a serious problem. New methods, means, forms and principles of training have a significant impact on the intellectual activity and emotional sphere of cadets.

Means of physical culture in the regulation of mental performance, psycho-emotional and functional states of cadets play a key role.

Physical exercises are of great educational importance - they contribute to strengthening discipline, increasing a sense of responsibility, developing perseverance in achieving the goal.

A high level of physical fitness determines a greater degree of resistance of the body to the effects of training loads, especially in conditions of emotionally stressful educational work. There are also lower energy costs when performing work.

Among the measures aimed at improving the mental performance of cadets, overcoming and preventing psychoemotional and functional overstrain, we can recommend the following:

- organization of a rational work regime, nutrition, sleep and rest;
- giving up bad habits: alcohol and drug use, smoking and substance abuse;
- physical training, constant maintenance of the body in a state of optimal physical fitness;
- training of cadets in methods of self-monitoring of the state of the body in order to identify deviations from the norm and timely correction and elimination of these deviations by means of prevention;
- the use of physical exercises as a means of active recreation;
- the use of "small forms" of physical culture in the mode of educational work of cadets, such as morning gymnastics, physical training pause, micropauses in the educational work of cadets using physical exercises (physical training minutes).

In the process of learning, young people should constantly develop healthy lifestyle skills. It must be remembered that systematic physical education and sports preserve youth, health, and longevity, which are accompanied by a creative labor upsurge. The observance of hygienic standards, the creation of a good psychological climate in student groups, the stimulation of mass physical culture, the correct organization of working hours are the necessary conditions for a healthy lifestyle. A conscious attitude to physical exercise is of great importance.

The physical culture of the individual manifests itself in three main directions. Firstly, it determines the ability to self-development, reflects the orientation of the individual "to himself", which is due to his social and spiritual experience, ensures his desire for creative "self-building", self-improvement. Secondly, physical culture is the basis of an amateur, initiative self-expression of a future specialist, a

manifestation of creativity in the use of physical culture tools aimed at the subject and its process professional work. Thirdly, it reflects the creativity of the individual, aimed at the relationships that arise in the process of physical culture, sports, social and professional activities, i.e. "on others". The richer and wider the circle of personal connections in this activity, the richer the space of its subjective manifestations becomes.

A comprehensive solution to the problems of physical education ensures the readiness of graduates for more active industrial activity, the ability to master skills faster, master new labor professions.

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